

Prediction and Optimization of Surface Roughness and MRR in Ti-6Al-4V Turning using a Deep Neural Network Regressor

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Abstract. Optimizing machining parameters for Ti-6Al-4V turning remains challenging due to conflicting objectives between surface quality and productivity. This study presents an integrated framework combining deep neural network regression (DNNR) with multi-objective evolutionary optimization to simultaneously predict and optimize surface roughness (R_a) and material removal rate (MRR). A Box-Behnken design with 15 experimental runs was conducted using three cutting parameters: cutting speed (40-60 m/min), feed rate (0.05-0.2 mm/rev), and depth of cut (0.2-1.2 mm).

The developed DNNR model demonstrated exceptional predictive accuracy with R^2 values of 0.934 for R_a and 0.998 for MRR, validating its effectiveness as a surrogate model. Subsequently, the Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm II (NSGA-II) was employed to generate a Pareto front of 33 optimal solutions, revealing critical trade-offs between surface finish and productivity. Sensitivity analysis identified cutting speed as the most influential parameter, followed by feed rate with pronounced nonlinear effects.

To facilitate decision-making, entropy-based TOPSIS ranking was applied to the Pareto solutions, yielding optimal cutting parameters of $V_c = 40.092$ m/min, $f_z = 0.097$ mm/rev, and $a_p = 0.210$ mm with predicted $R_a = 0.021$ μm and MRR = 0.017 cm^3/min . This top-ranked solution achieved a TOPSIS score of 1.000, representing the ideal balance between minimal surface roughness and acceptable productivity. The proposed DNNR-NSGA-II-TOPSIS framework significantly reduces experimental requirements while providing reliable optimization for Ti-6Al-4V turning operations, making it suitable for aerospace and biomedical manufacturing applications.

Keywords: Ti-6Al-4V Machining, Deep Neural Network Regressor, Multi-Objective Optimization.

1 Introduction

Titanium alloys, particularly Ti-6Al-4V, are widely used in aerospace, biomedical, and high-performance engineering due to their excellent strength-to-weight ratio, corrosion resistance, and biocompatibility [1]. However, machining Ti-6Al-4V presents several challenges, including rapid tool wear, high cutting temperatures, and difficulties in achieving the desired surface quality and productivity [2], [3]. Hence, optimizing the cutting parameters to enhance surface finish (R_a) and material removal rate (MRR) remains a critical objective in precision manufacturing [4], [5].

Numerous studies have explored the use of statistical models and machine learning techniques to predict and optimize machining responses. Traditional methods such as response surface methodology (RSM) [6], artificial neural networks (ANN) [7], and support vector regression (SVR) [8] [4] have shown promising results in specific applications. However, with the growing complexity of machining dynamics and the demand for multi-objective optimization, more flexible and expressive models are needed.

To address these challenges, various multi-objective decision-making (MCDM) techniques and evolutionary algorithms (EAs) have been investigated. Among prominent MCDM approaches [9], [10], TOPSIS [4], [7], [11], VIKOR, and entropy-based methods have been applied for ranking machining alternatives [12], [13], [14]. Concurrently, evolutionary optimization techniques, including Non-Dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm (NSGA), NSGA-II, NSGA-III [5], [15], NSGA-PO [16], Strength Pareto Evolutionary Algorithm (SPEA2) [17], Multi-Objective Particle Swarm Optimization (MOPSO) [18], and hybrid approaches combining Genetic Algorithm (GA) with Simulated Annealing (SA) or Differential Evolution (DE), have demonstrated effectiveness in generating Pareto-optimal solutions for machining optimization problems [19], [20], [21]. However, these methods frequently exhibit computational inefficiency, premature convergence, and dependence on extensive experimental datasets for reliable predictive model development.

In this study, a deep learning-based regression framework is developed to simultaneously predict surface roughness and material removal rate during the turning of Ti-6Al-4V. The model architecture is based on a feedforward neural network trained with experimental data comprising three input parameters: cutting speed (V_c), feed rate (f_z), and depth of cut (a_p). The predictive model is configured and trained to achieve high accuracy and generalization capability, enabling its application in intelligent process parameter selection and multi-objective machining optimization.

Furthermore, a Pareto-based multi-objective optimization framework is applied to identify optimal trade-offs between minimizing surface roughness and maximizing material removal rate. The proposed approach demonstrates the effectiveness of deep neural networks in machining applications and provides a practical tool for intelligent process parameter selection in titanium alloy turning.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Experimental Design and Setup

All collected experimental results, including R_a and computed MRR values, are listed in Table 2.

Table 1. Experimental Matrix and Measured Responses

V_c	f_z	a_p	R_a	MRR
60	0.125	1.2	1.829	0.5087
50	0.125	0.7	0.902	0.2473
40	0.125	1.2	0.86	0.3391
50	0.2	0.2	1.137	0.113
60	0.2	0.7	1.615	0.4748
40	0.2	0.7	0.615	0.3165
50	0.05	0.2	0.944	0.0283
60	0.05	0.7	1.551	0.1187
40	0.05	0.7	0.304	0.0791
50	0.2	1.2	1.401	0.6782
50	0.125	0.2	0.637	0.0707
50	0.125	1.2	1.037	0.4239
50	0.125	0.7	0.978	0.2473
60	0.125	0.7	1.147	0.2967
40	0.125	0.2	0.3	0.0565

2.2 Optimization Framework

This study employs an integrated optimization framework that combines data-driven modeling with multi-objective evolutionary search and decision-making to determine optimal cutting parameters in Ti-6Al-4V turning. The framework is designed to simultaneously minimize surface roughness (R_a) and maximize material removal rate (MRR), ensuring a balanced machining performance.

Fig. 1. DNNR Modeling Framework

Non-Dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm II (NSGA-II)

Fig. 2. Flowchart of NSGA-II evolutionary process with elitism and Pareto-based ranking

Entropy-Based TOPSIS for Solution Ranking.

The optimization process for machining Ti-6Al-4V followed a systematic decision-making workflow using entropy-weighted TOPSIS. Cutting parameters—cutting speed (V_c), feed rate (f_z), and depth of cut (a_p), were first evaluated based on their predicted outcomes (R_a and MRR) generated by the DNNR model. The decision matrix was

normalized and weighted using entropy values, with R_a assigned a slightly higher importance due to its variability across Pareto-optimal solutions. Alternatives were ranked based on their relative closeness to the ideal solution. The overall procedure is illustrated in Figure 3. The step-by-step calculation and mathematical formulation of the TOPSIS with entropy weight method are presented in detail in [14].

Fig. 3. Flowchart of the Entropy-TOPSIS decision making process for multi-criteria optimization

Integrated Optimization Framework for Ti-6Al-4V Turning.

To effectively optimize the turning process of Ti-6Al-4V alloy, this study proposes an integrated framework that combines data-driven modeling and advanced multi-objective optimization techniques. The core of this approach is a deep neural network regressor (DNRR), which serves as a predictive surrogate model for estimating surface roughness (R_a) and material removal rate (MRR) based on machining inputs—cutting speed (V_c), feed rate (f_z), and depth of cut (a_p). The DNRR is trained using experimentally collected data and achieves high predictive accuracy, enabling reliable virtual evaluations of untested parameter combinations.

Following model training, a global search for optimal parameters is conducted using the Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm II (NSGA-II). This evolutionary algorithm iteratively evolves a population of candidate solutions through genetic operations, guided by Pareto dominance and diversity preservation. The output is a set of non-

dominated solutions that represent trade-offs between minimizing R_a and maximizing MRR.

Fig. 4. Optimization Workflow with DNNR, NSGA-II and Entropy-TOPSIS

To assist in selecting the most appropriate cutting conditions from the Pareto front, the Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS) is employed. In this study, TOPSIS is enhanced with entropy-based weighting to account for the relative dispersion and importance of each objective. The final optimal solution is identified as the one closest to the ideal point, representing minimal surface roughness and maximal productivity.

This integrated DNNR–NSGA-II–TOPSIS framework enables both predictive modeling and multi-criteria decision-making, offering a robust and efficient solution for improving Ti-6Al-4V machining performance while minimizing the need for extensive experimental trials.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Regression and Model Validation

Fig. 5. Comparison of actual and predicted surface roughness (R_a) using the trained DNNR model.

Fig. 6. Comparison of actual and predicted material removal rate (MRR) using the trained DNNR model.

3.2 DNNR Surrogate Model Evaluation

Fig. 7. Pareto-optimal distribution of R_a and MRR colored by cutting parameters: (a) cutting speed (V_c), (b) feed rate (f_z), and (c) depth of cut (a_p)

3.3 Multi-objective Optimization

To simultaneously optimize surface roughness (R_a) and material removal rate (MRR), a multi-objective optimization strategy was implemented by integrating a deep neural network regressor (DNNR) with the Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm II (NSGA-II). All modeling and optimization tasks were carried out in MATLAB 2023b,

utilizing built-in toolboxes such as Neural Network Toolbox for regression and Global Optimization Toolbox for evolutionary search.

Fig. 8. The Pareto front was generated using the trained DNNR model integrated with NSGA-II evolutionary optimization

Fig. 9. 3D-Pareto front with solutions by predicted surface roughness (R_a).

Fig. 10. 3D-Pareto front with solutions by predicted material removal rate (MRR)

Table 2. Ranked Pareto-optimal solutions obtained by NSGA-II and evaluated using Entropy-based TOPSIS method

No	V_c	f_z	a_p	R_a predict	MRR predict	TOPSIS Score	TOPSIS Rank
40.092	0.097	0.210	-0.021	0.017	1.000	1	
40.121	0.106	0.527	0.074	0.087	0.918	2	
40.111	0.113	0.547	0.188	0.108	0.865	3	
40.105	0.111	0.615	0.200	0.129	0.848	4	
40.104	0.105	0.679	0.263	0.143	0.816	5	

No	V_c	f_z	a_p	R_a predict	MRR predict	TOPSIS Score	TOPSIS Rank
40.343	0.111	0.708	0.308	0.159	0.789	6	
40.336	0.116	0.748	0.350	0.177	0.762	7	
40.104	0.103	0.807	0.421	0.183	0.732	8	
40.271	0.121	0.788	0.440	0.199	0.715	9	
40.238	0.122	0.881	0.505	0.230	0.673	10	
40.321	0.116	0.919	0.555	0.235	0.651	11	
40.288	0.126	0.958	0.602	0.260	0.618	12	
40.011	0.127	0.994	0.624	0.273	0.602	13	
40.396	0.127	1.025	0.674	0.283	0.578	14	
40.297	0.129	1.082	0.733	0.304	0.543	15	
40.103	0.134	1.097	0.774	0.316	0.521	16	
40.378	0.136	1.180	0.868	0.346	0.469	17	
40.065	0.141	1.174	0.923	0.354	0.445	18	
40.497	0.141	1.184	0.952	0.357	0.434	19	
40.430	0.145	1.191	1.002	0.366	0.412	20	
40.114	0.152	1.178	1.074	0.373	0.385	21	
40.113	0.153	1.196	1.088	0.377	0.378	22	
46.513	0.143	1.142	1.175	0.403	0.335	23	
43.305	0.165	1.157	1.213	0.403	0.326	24	
48.148	0.143	1.131	1.229	0.446	0.290	25	
47.342	0.165	1.173	1.293	0.511	0.225	26	
48.358	0.161	1.193	1.304	0.530	0.207	27	
49.125	0.173	1.195	1.343	0.585	0.153	28	
51.222	0.166	1.095	1.380	0.592	0.140	29	
51.416	0.169	1.177	1.382	0.625	0.111	30	
49.593	0.196	1.172	1.391	0.652	0.086	31	
51.204	0.191	1.107	1.419	0.663	0.072	32	
54.913	0.196	1.193	1.464	0.734	0.000	33	

4 Conclusion

This study successfully developed and validated an integrated optimization framework combining deep neural network regression (DNNR) with multi-objective evolutionary algorithms for Ti-6Al-4V turning operations. The developed DNNR model demonstrated exceptional predictive accuracy with R^2 values of 0.934 for surface roughness (R_a) and 0.998 for material removal rate (MRR), respectively. The high adjusted R^2

values (0.916 and 0.997) confirmed the model's robust generalization capability and reliability as a surrogate model for machining optimization. The tight clustering of predicted versus actual values and near-zero error distributions validated the model's effectiveness in capturing complex nonlinear relationships between cutting parameters and machining responses.

Building upon this predictive foundation, the NSGA-II optimization successfully generated a well-distributed Pareto front, revealing critical trade-offs between surface quality and productivity. Sensitivity analysis identified cutting speed (V_c) as the most influential parameter affecting both objectives, followed by feed rate (f_z) with pronounced nonlinear effects, while depth of cut (a_p) showed minimal impact on surface roughness but contributed linearly to MRR enhancement. These findings align with established machining principles, reinforcing the physical plausibility of the optimization framework.

To facilitate practical decision-making from the Pareto solutions, the integration of entropy-based TOPSIS provided a systematic approach for ranking solutions based on multiple criteria. The entropy weighting scheme (0.5432 for R_a , 0.4568 for MRR) effectively captured the relative importance of each objective, enabling practical decision-making for different production scenarios. The ranked solutions offer manufacturers flexibility in selecting optimal parameters based on specific quality-productivity requirements.

From an industrial perspective, the proposed DNNR-NSGA II-TOPSIS framework significantly reduces the need for extensive experimental trials while maintaining high prediction accuracy. This approach enables rapid virtual evaluation of machining parameters, supporting intelligent process planning and real-time optimization in Ti-6Al-4V manufacturing. The methodology's computational efficiency and reliability make it suitable for industrial implementation in aerospace and biomedical applications where titanium alloy machining is critical.

However, certain limitations should be acknowledged to guide future research directions. The current study is limited to a specific range of cutting parameters and single pass turning operations under dry cutting conditions. Future work should investigate the framework's applicability under different cooling strategies, including minimum quantity lubrication (MQL) and cryogenic cooling. Additionally, incorporating tool wear progression and extending the model to other titanium alloys would enhance the framework's industrial relevance. Investigation of advanced neural network architectures, such as attention mechanisms or transformer-based models, could further improve prediction accuracy for complex machining scenarios.

In conclusion, this research establishes a comprehensive data-driven optimization methodology that effectively addresses the challenges of Ti-6Al-4V machining while providing practical tools for industrial implementation. The integration of advanced machine learning techniques with evolutionary optimization represents a significant advancement in intelligent manufacturing systems, offering both academic insights and practical solutions for precision machining of difficult-to-cut materials.

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